

Acknowledgement

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Stabilisation of Molybdenyl Cation(V) in Diverse Anionic Environment by 2(2'-Pyridyl) benzimidazole

H. K. SAHA, (Miss) ANIMA SAHA and S. S. MANDAL

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

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WE have reported in details¹⁻² the chemistry of MoO⁵⁺ in the environment of some diverse anions. The present communication deals with the isolation and study of some oxomolybdenum(V)chloro complexes with 2(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazole (Pybmz) in spin-free state.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared following the standard procedure³ and the other reagents used were of A.R. grade. Molybdenum and chloride were estimated gravimetrically as molybdenum trioxide and silver chloride. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method. The oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method.

2(2'-Pyridyl) benzimidazoliumoxopentachloromolybdate(V), PybmzH₂ [MoOCl₅]:

Molybdenum trioxide (~1 g) was dissolved in HCl (10 ml, 12 M) with stirring followed by addition of hydriodic acid (1 ml). The solution was boiled to drive off the liberated iodine. The concentrated small mass was taken up with minimum quantity of conc.HCl when a bright green solution was obtained. To this solution containing MoOCl₅²⁻, was added with stirring a solution of 0.8 g ligand in minimum quantity of HCl when a greenish yellow precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered and dried *in vacuo* over solid KOH to yield the product (1.9 g).

Oxotrichloro [2 (2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole]molybdenum(V), [MoOCl₃.Pybmz], (pink): A sample of the parent salt, PybmzH₂ [MoOCl₅] (~1 g) was refluxed with dehydrated ethanol (15 ml) for 0.5 h. The pink coloured crystalline solid so formed was filtered and dried *in vacuo* over solid KOH to yield the product (0.75 g).

Oxotrichloro [2 (2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole]molybdenum(V), [MoOCl₃.Pybmz], (orange): The orange coloured crystalline compound was obtained by refluxing 1g of the original salt (1g) with acetonitrile (15 ml) for 2 h. The solid mass was filtered, washed with acetonitrile and dried *in vacuo* to yield the product (0.73 g).

Alternatively, the orange compound was also prepared by refluxing the parent salt with acetylacetone for 2.5 h. Analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The extensive hydrolysis and ionisation of oxopentahalomolybdate(V) ion was confirmed by conductance measurement of the salt in aqueous medium. The non-electrolytic nature of [MoOCl₅.Pybmz] compound was established by conductance measurement in acetonitrile. The conductance values in 10⁻³M solution of the pink and the orange forms are 11.73 and 11.28, 11.68 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, respectively which are much less than those for binary electrolytes⁴.

The μ_{eff} values of the complexes, PybmzH₂ [MoOCl₅], [MoOCl₃.Pybmz] (pink) and [MoOCl₃.Pybmz] (orange, two product) are 1.51, 1.62, 1.53

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, OXIDATION STATE, MAGNETIC AND CONDUCTANCE DATA FOR OXOMOLYBDENUM(V) COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Oxidation state	μ _{eff} B.M.	Molar conductance Ω ⁻¹
		Mo	Cl	N			
PybmzH ₂ [MoOCl ₅]	Greenish yellow	20.32 (19.72)	35.69 (36.48)	9.43 (8.68)	5.07	1.513	—
[MoOCl ₅ .Pybmz]	Pink	23.82 (23.23)	25.72 (25.78)	10.56 (10.16)	4.89	1.62	11.73
[MoOCl ₃ .Pybmz]	Orange	23.74 (23.23)	25.87 (25.78)	10.76 (10.16)	4.88	1.53	11.28
[MoOCl ₃ .Pybmz] (from acetylacetone)	Orange	23.73 (23.23)	25.80 (25.78)	9.91 (10.16)	4.91	1.46	11.68

and 1.46 B.M., respectively (Table 1). It appears from the result that the salt and both the varieties of mononuclear complex contain quinquivalent molybdenum having d^1 configurations. The ir spectrum of the salt, $\text{PymbzH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ shows a strong band at 980 cm^{-1} while for both the varieties of non-electrolyte it appears at 975 cm^{-1} . These bands can be assigned to the terminal $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ vibration⁵. The lowering of stretching frequencies by 5 cm^{-1} , from salt to non-electrolyte, may probably be due to the strong donating capabilities of the nitrogen atom of the ligand and thus causing increased electron density around the central metal atom and reducing its π -acceptance capacity and ultimately the metal oxygen bond strength.

The uv and visible spectra of the salt were recorded in 12 M HCl while for the other in acetonitrile medium. The observed results clearly agree with the previous observation^{6,7}.

The salt, 2(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazoliumoxopentachloromolybdate(V) in 12 M HCl shows two crystal field transitions around $14000\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(I))}$ and $22000\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1)$, and three charge transfer transitions around $27000\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(II))}$, $34000\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_2\text{(I))}$ and $43000\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(III))}$, respectively. Similarly, for both the varieties of non-electrolyte the bands appear around 13000, 19000, 27000, 33000 and 42000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transitions, $^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(I)}$, $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{Mo}$ charge transfer, $^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1$, $^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_2\text{(I)}$ and $^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(III)}$, respectively.

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Oxovanadium(IV) and Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes with Dioxime of Fluorene Glyoxal

U. K. SRIVASTAVA, B. S. YADAV and D. R. SINGH

Chemical Research Laboratory, R. B. S. College, Agra-282 002

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OF many oxo metal species studied, VO^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} are the most stable^{1,2}. Both the ions form various types of stable complexes with different ligands. The complexes of VO^{2+}

with macrocyclic ligands³ derived from 2,6-dipicolinoaldihydrazine and β -diketones have been studied. The electron spin resonance studies on dihalogenovanadium(IV) having different ground states are some recent revelations⁴.

The complexes of dioxouranium(VI) with many monobasic bidentate and dibasic tetradentate Schiff bases have been studied recently⁵ and many interesting features pertaining to their physico-chemical aspects have been divulged. Aforesaid investigations led to synthesise a new ligand and its complexes with oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) ions. In the present investigation we have isolated oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes of fluorene glyoxal dioxime and characterised them with the help of elemental analysis, magnetic moment, ir and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade and the solvents were purified by distillation.

Preparation of ligand: Fluorene glyoxal was obtained from fluorene by its acetylation and subsequent oxidation by selenium dioxide⁶.

Dioxime of fluorene glyoxal was prepared by refluxing hydroxylamine hydrochloride and fluorene glyoxal in molar ratio of 2 : 1 in an aqueous NaOH solution for about 30 min. After cooling in ice-bath, 2-3 ml of water was added to get brownish black precipitate. After washing with water it was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 160°).

Preparation of complexes: Oxovanadyl(IV) complex was prepared by refluxing aqueous ethanolic solutions of vanadyl chloride and ligand in molar ratio of 1 : 2. The green precipitate thus obtained was filtered and washed with aqueous ethanol and finally dried at 120° .

Dioxouranium(VI) complex was prepared by mixing ethanolic solution of dioxime with uranyl iodide solution in ethanol. Uranyl iodide was prepared by methathesis (addition of KI to uranyl acetate). The yellow crystalline complex separated out was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on Beckman and Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer at Department of Chemistry, Delhi University, and Textile and Chemistry Department, I.I.T., New Delhi. The magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature on Gouy balance. Electronic spectra in solution were recorded on Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by microanalytical methods. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method, vanadium and uranium by conventional gravimetric methods (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The ligand was found to be brownish black in colour and stable. It showed bidentate nature in all the complexes. In oxovanadium(IV) complex